

Abstract

It is shown that the conclusion about the existence of a plane electromagnetic wave of transverse type, as a consequence of Maxwell's equations, is not correct.

It is considered, what unsurmountable difficulties arise, if an electromagnetic wave is formed by Photons possessing wave properties, conditionally named Hooke's Photons. Accordingly, the very existence of Photons with wave properties is also put under great doubt.

It is concluded that the structure of the electromagnetic radiation of an antenna can be explained if it is formed by Photons that do not possess wave properties [4], conventionally named Newton's Photons.

Key words: photon, wave properties, Maxwell's equations

The plane electromagnetic wave as a consequence of Maxwell's equations

In some technical sections of physics until now there is an idea of an electromagnetic wave as a certain unity of electric and magnetic components, mutually stabilizing each other, and freely propagating in space. In the concrete practice of using electromagnetic waves, the elucidation of the true nature of the wave is not always required, which is quite justified. However, on closer examination, it turns out that such a model is based on an erroneous consequence of Maxwell's equations.

All quantities in Maxwell's equations are related by ratios:

$\vec{B} = \mu_0 \vec{H}$, $\vec{D} = \epsilon_0 \vec{E}$, $\vec{j} = \sigma \vec{E}$. Here \vec{B} is the magnetic induction, whose formula takes into account the effect of the magnetic permeability of the substance μ_0 on the strength \vec{H} of the magnetic field, \vec{D} is the electric induction, \vec{E} is the electric field, \vec{j} is the electric current density. Other quantities - constants, characterize the properties of the substance

Maxwell's equations, since their appearance, have changed their presentation form more than once, but have not changed their physical meaning, which was based on the experiments of M. Faraday. Now, based on the achieved level of knowledge, it can be argued that the physical justification requires correction. The correction is based on a reliable fact: the charge of the Electron does not exist independently in a free form, and is inseparable from the Electron - particle. The same follows from the Electron model [4]. Based on the strict application of this property of Electrons, another physical meaning of Faraday's experiments is given below.

The physical meaning of the first two equations does not require additional explanation:

$$\operatorname{div}\vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\varepsilon_0}, \quad (1)$$

an electric field is created by electric charges.

$$\operatorname{div}\vec{B} = 0, \quad (2)$$

magnetic charges do not exist.

The physical meaning of the other two equations needs to be explained.

$$\operatorname{rot}\vec{B} = \mu_0\vec{j} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{d\vec{D}}{dt}, \quad (3)$$

the vortex magnetic field is generated by the movement of charges (electric current \vec{j}) and/or by a change in the electric field (in this case in the form of a change in induction, $\vec{D} = \varepsilon_0\vec{E}$).

An experiment that proves that a magnetic field is formed as a result of a change in induction is the transmission of alternating current (called bias current) through the plates of a capacitor. And from here, apparently, the conclusion follows that the vortex magnetic field is generated by an alternating electric field. Such an erroneous conclusion is possible if we separate the physical nature of the phenomenon from its symbolic designation. The reason for the appearance of an alternating magnetic field near the capacitor is the real accumulation (resorption) current of Electrons on its plates or the polarization current of the dielectric. Thus, in this case, the magnetic field also appears only as a result of the movement of charges, and it would be a mistake to consider the appearance of a magnetic field outside the movement of charges

It should be borne in mind that the vortex nature of the Magnetic field is a secondary effect [4], and is created automatically from elementary magnetic field vectors, the conflict-free existence of which is possible only in the form of ring structures. The primary effect is the orthogonality of the elementary magnetic field vectors to the electric field lines.

The following formula states, variable induction of magnetic field creates a vortex electric field.

$$\operatorname{rot}\vec{E} = -\frac{d\vec{B}}{dt} \quad (4)$$

In this form, formula (4) at the level of physical meaning comes into conflict with the first (1) Maxwell equation. The contradiction is that the electric field (vortex, or any other) is created by charges, and not by a change in the magnetic field strength. The vortex electric field, in the sense in which it exists in relation to the magnetic field, does not exist. Electric field lines do not create closed concentric circles. In fact, the induction created by an alternating magnetic field creates a force that causes electrons in a conductor to move in a direction orthogonal to the magnetic field lines. Consequently, an alternating current will arise in a closed conductor located in an alternating

magnetic field. The assumption about the vortex nature of the electric field is nothing more than a tribute to tradition.

Therefore, given that $\vec{j} = \sigma \vec{E}$, it would be more correct to write

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} \text{rot} \vec{j} = -\frac{d\vec{B}}{dt} \quad (5)$$

This means that a change in the magnetic field induction creates conditionally eddy currents (in fact, the currents are orthogonal to the magnetic field lines) in a conductor (in any other conducting medium), and then they create a conditionally eddy electric field. Without a conductor, eddy currents, and therefore an eddy electric field, do not exist. Moreover, a priori formula (4) makes sense if the magnetic field acts on a region having charges, and thus returns us to Maxwell's first (1) formula. Mathematically both formulas (5) and (4) are equivalent, but from a physical point of view the formulas are completely different. Nevertheless, it is the physically incorrect formula (4) together with formula (3) that allowed concluding about a stable, freely propagating electromagnetic field in space. The judgment is simple. A change in electrical induction creates a variable magnetic field, and a variable magnetic induction, in turn, creates a variable electric field. Its stability, according to the formulas, is ensured by the mutual stabilizing directionality of the electric and magnetic components, and thus both components remain unchanged. If to be guided by physically correct formula (5) and formula (3) it is obvious that in vacuum, where there are no charges, **stable electromagnetic radiation of the above type cannot exist.**

Based on the above, Hooke's Photon model in the form of a plane electromagnetic wave is questionable.

Plane electromagnetic wave as a flow of Hooke's Photons

The consequence of Maxwell's equations was the basis for the creation of the physical image of the Photon **as a plane electromagnetic wave of transverse type**. A superficial look at the phenomena of interference as if also indicates the presence of wave properties in the Photon. In addition, interference phenomena also directly indicate the presence of wave properties in the Photon (such a Photon can be called Hooke's Photon). The result was a model of a plane electromagnetic wave in the form of a stream of Photons, **each of which is also a plane electromagnetic wave of transverse type**. This wave model was advocated by R. Hooke; accordingly, the Photon was called Hooke's Photon.

Figure 1 shows the Photon packet forming an electromagnetic wave at the output of the antenna. According to existing ideas, the fundamental frequency of Photons in the radiation packet repeats the frequency of the sinusoid fed to the antenna input (solid line).

The figure shows how in a packet of electromagnetic radiation the total vector of the electrical component (indicated by arrows of different lengths) changes its magnitude and direction

in accordance with the input signal. It can be seen how the total vector of the electrical component of one direction changes to the vector of the opposite direction. A longer arrow quantitatively corresponds to a greater number of Photons participating in the radiation

Fig. 1

However, this model does not stand up to criticism. It is impossible to explain the “birth” of a very complex Photon particle in a simple act of radiation. It is unclear how the **neutral** particle Photon interacts with the **charged** particle Electron. The question about stability of a particle in absorption-radiation cycles also remains unanswered. For example, if the Photon is stable, how and where does the Electron find, capture and then emit the Photon. A critical look at this phenomenon suggests looking for a related nature of particles, which does not follow from the wave model of Photon. The connection between the frequency of the signal at the antenna input and the frequency of the emitted Photons is also not obvious; in this case, their frequencies must coincide. It is impossible to explain how this happens. The frequency **spectrum of the radiation does not follow from the frequency of the input voltage**. There is absolutely no clarity on the question of whether the emission spectrum depends on the amplitude of the input voltage.

Thus, it is highly doubtful that this model of a plane electromagnetic wave corresponds to real radiation. Consequently, the existence of wave properties in Photons is also questioned.

Model of Newton's Photon

Structure of Newton's Photon and Electron

The corpuscular model of the Photon was defended by I. Newton. Therefore, a Photon without wave properties is conventionally called Newton’s Photon in the article.

Newton's hypothetical Photon [4] should have the following properties.

The photon is eternal. It follows from this that instead of the “absorption” of Photons by matter, the concept of “capture” would be more correct. Accordingly, instead of the term “birth”, another term should be used, for example, “radiation”. Further, it is logical to assume that the Universe “floats” in a sea of Photons of different energies. Low-frequency, low-energy Photons fill

the entire world space, “impregnate” matter to any depth, interact with all charges, wherever they are, and ultimately form the background Mass. The structure of the Photon must be such that, under certain conditions and specific reactions, Photons can be converted into Electrons and Positrons. This would explain the fact of the interaction of charge-neutral Photons with Electrons or Positrons. Below we consider a model of the Photon which satisfies these conditions and which represents two interconnected Charges of different polarity.

Structurally, a Photon is a particle representing two interconnected Charges of different polarity [3].

Fig. 2 shows the assumed structure of Photon at the moment of its conditional destruction into two parts.

Fig. 2

This structure explains the overall neutral charge of the Photon, its electromagnetic properties, polarization, interaction with the Electron, stability and other properties. An Electron is a Charge (negative) and a Shell [4]

Photon and quantum nonlocality

In modern discussions about the principle of interaction between particles, the properties of the proposed Photon model **correspond to that part of Bell's inequalities** in which the principle of quantum nonlocality [1] is realized (information about localization of a particle passes with a speed higher than the speed of light, and as a consequence, properties of particles are not determined before the moment of interaction). This follows from the fact that due to the hypothetical mechanism of particle formation [4], particles have real and imaginary parts. The interaction between particles takes place in the imaginary part of the complex space, hence with a velocity higher than the speed of light, and only then is reflected in the real space in the form of particle displacement (possibly due to the Bell potential) [2]. The imaginary parts of all particles exist in the entire imaginary space, all particles are always inextricably linked with each other. Applied to the study of electromagnetic waves, this means that the Electrons of the antenna, due to the quantum

nonlocality of the Charge (in the original text - the spatial uncertainty of the Charge), will always find a suitable Photon in space to capture it, pump it with energy, and then radiate it.

Mechanism of spatial anisotropy and polarization

It is known that the Photon is asymmetric in the plane orthogonal to the axis of its propagation. As shown by many experiments, there is a certain **narrow sector** in this plane relative to the axis of propagation, where the Photon quite definitely shows itself as an **integral particle**.

The sharply asymmetrical structure of the Photon was called spatial Anisotropy of the Photon. In classical physics, spatial anisotropy is associated with the plane of periodic oscillations of the vector of the electrical component. In the hypothesis there is no concept of a constantly oscillating vector of the electrical component and, accordingly, the spatial anisotropy of the Photon is caused by another reason.

According to the hypothesis, when the Photon moves in space, a magnetic field is formed around each Charge forming the Photon. Elementary magnetic vectors around the center of the Photon form an interconnected system, the magnetic field. The structure of the system (magnetic field) is known from experiments, the elementary vectors form concentric circles in the plane **orthogonal** to the conductor. In the case when two charges of different polarity move in the same direction, according to M. Faraday's laws, the elementary magnetic vectors in the concentric circles of one of the charges will be directed opposite to the elementary vectors of the other charge in the entire region around both charges. This state is a conflict. The only conflict-free place for elementary magnetic vectors can be a straight line, orthogonal to the axis of displacement. The elementary magnetic vectors of both charges, located along this straight line, will be directed equally, forming a total magnetic field vector. The total vector of the magnetic field, like its elementary components, also has the property of spatial certainty. This means that it has geometric dimensions and is capable of mechanically interacting with matter. It is this property that gives rise to the effect of **spatial anisotropy**.

The concept of polarization of light is applicable to the flow of Photons and means that the plane of spatial anisotropy for all Photons in the flow, under the influence of certain factors, periodically changes (or does not change) according to the same law. Consequently, it is meaningless to apply this concept to an individual Photon, since the conditional vector of the electrical component does not undergo periodic oscillations.

Photon mass and interaction cross section

Since the magnetic component of the Photon is a form of potential energy, it is logical to assume that one of its manifestations is the Photon Mass. Indeed, from observations it follows that the Photon, when interacting with Electrons, transfers to them a certain impulse, in the formal

expression of which there are two quantities: Mass and speed. The symbolic expression of momentum is the formula $P=mc$. There is a certain peculiarity in the understanding of this formula. The impulse is transmitted in the direction of velocity. But the Photon is a special particle, and transfers momentum orthogonally to the direction of its velocity. Consequently, the maximum speed of the Photon's traveling in the real space cannot be related to this formula.

In this case, the formula specifies the **minimum** velocity of interaction propagation in **imaginary space**, which is equal to the **maximum** velocity **in real space**. Thus, everything falls into place, and Mass is one of the forms of manifestation of the magnetic component of the Photon. Being materialized energy, Mass exists as a property of the structure and must have spatially defined parameters, first of all, linear size in the direction orthogonal to the axis of movement of the particle. Experiments show that as the relative velocity increases, the cross-section of particle interaction increases geometrically. Photon is no exception.

It is noticed that the interaction cross section grows in the direction orthogonal to the velocity. The spatially defined parameter can belong only to the magnetic component of the Photon. Hence, the interaction cross section is another property of the magnetic component of the Photon. The greater the Photon energy, i.e. Mass, the greater the interaction cross-section, the more pronounced the polarization and its effect on the Electrons in the antenna becomes.

Polarization, Anisotropy, Interaction cross-section, Mass are different sides of the same phenomenon - existence of a magnetic component in the Photon.

In the 4-dimensional representation, the acceleration (force) vector is orthogonal to the velocity vector.

Fig. 3

Fig. 3 shows 3 vectors, the Spin S (determines the direction of motion in space), the Force vector M (the materialized potential energy of the Photon in the form of mass), and the conditional, not really existing vector of the electrical component of the Photon E , which determines the direction of motion of the electrons in the antenna.

All vectors are orthogonal. The mass of the Photon is not a source of momentum in the direction of motion, hence the pressure of light on matter must have a spin nature.

A plane electromagnetic wave as a stream of photons that have no wave properties.

Signal reception by antenna

If the radiation is formed by Newtonian Photons, then the reception and emission of the signal by the antenna is based on the following principle.

Photons in the stream, falling on the antenna conductor, are captured by Electrons. The capture of Photons by Electrons is based on their related nature and the polarized state of Photons. Captured by the shell of the Electron, the Photon forms a Photon-Electron pair, the positive Charge of the Photon neutralizes the charge of the Electron, but the negative Charge of the Photon leaves the total charge of the complex particle Photon-Electron invariably negative.

The Photon, being activated in the antenna, due to its potential energy in the form of magnetic component will create an impulse orthogonal to its previous direction of motion and to magnetic component, which will make the Electron in the antenna move along the conductor. The impulse corresponds to the conditional vector of the electric component of the Photon.

The modulated Photon flux density will create a variable voltage in the antenna.

Radiation of an electromagnetic wave

Radiation is based on the effect that when braking or changing another parameter (changing the configuration of the electric field or the direction of the magnetic moment of the Electron, etc.) **the Electron drops the captured Photon into space, giving it its energy.**

Since the Electron has a magnetic moment, it is natural to assume that under the influence of the electric field at the antenna input, the spins of all free Electrons in the antenna conductor are oriented identically. Changing the current in the antenna to the opposite direction will change the orientation of all Electrons also to the opposite direction. For this reason, **Photons in space relative to the antenna will also be located equally.** This explains why the emitted Photons from the antenna scatter in directions orthogonal to the antenna conductor. In this case, the conditional vector of the electrical component of the Photon will be located either in the upper or lower half-plane. A flow of Electrons modulated in density and orientation in the antenna will create a flow of Photons in the space behind the antenna, with a variable orientation of the conditional vector of the electrical component.

Fig. 4

On figure 4 shows that the maximum flux of Photons is emitted at the moment the electric field strength at the antenna input changes to the opposite, since it is at this moment that both the Electron velocities and the direction of the magnetic moment change especially sharply. This is shown in the figure 4 by increased color density. The highest color density corresponds to the extreme of the sinusoidal voltage at the antenna input. The arrows show the location of the vector of the electrical component and the direction of the acceleration forces on the Electrons. Thus, **the antenna will emit a stream of Photons, modulated in density in accordance with the frequency of the signal at the antenna input.**

It is quite obvious that the frequency of the signal at the output of the transmitting antenna will always repeat the frequency of the input voltage, regardless of its amplitude. The spectral composition of the radiation at the output will always provide such a configuration of the Photon density that will repeat the configuration of the signal at the input.

In Figure 4, the density of the arrows reflects the density of Photons in the radiation, the same sense has a different intensity of coloring of the sectors, the more intense the coloring, the denser the flux of Photon. The direction of arrows united in groups conditionally shows the spatial location of the conditional vector of the electric component of the radiated Photon. As follows from the figure, there are no periodic changes in the length of the arrows. Accordingly, this Photon flux, hitting the receiving antenna, will systematically repeat all the changes of the Electron fluxes in the transmitting antenna.

Figure 5 shows the Photon flux radiated by antenna "A" in the "P" direction of receiving antenna "B". A photon orthogonally emitted by the transmitting antenna conductor and captured by the receiving antenna's Electron will impart a pulse to it that will cause the Electron to move along the receiving antenna conductor in either the forward or reverse direction (depending on the half-wave).

The index "G" denotes the oscillator, which generates the control voltage at the input of the transmitting antenna. The accelerating and decelerating effect of the electric field at the input of the transmitting antenna forms the photon flux in the space behind the antenna. The index "R" denotes

a receiver that shapes the voltage at its output according to the Photon flux density at the antenna input.

Fig. 5

Electromagnetic radiation, in which groups (packets) of Photons with upper and lower position of the vector of the electric component alternately change places, at a time interval of one period will create an impression that indeed some vector of the electric component makes periodic oscillations.

Thus, the plane electromagnetic wave of transverse type, in which the vector of the electric component makes periodic oscillations, is a consequence of the technological technique that was used to obtain it. In reality, radiation is a stream of Photons, each of which does not possess wave properties.

There are reasons to believe that in nature electromagnetic radiation is not formed in this way. The question whether this is true or not can be answered by using polarizers (if they exist) that can cut off the upper or lower half-wave. It would be interesting to use such polarizers to study radiation from distant stellar objects.

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